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Evaluation of the Implementation of New Framework Regulations for Engineering Education in Norway

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports on work to reshape the Norwegian bachelor of engineering education. It describes the process the reshaping is an important part of, several major findings of both positive and negative nature, and corresponding proposals for improvement in both the short and long run. Some of these findings are rooted in formal changes in the Norwegian educational system, while some of them arise from changes in society per se. Some of the proposals for improvement are easy to implement by individual institutions, while others require a tight cooperation between different institutions.

Conference Key Areas: Curriculum Development, Quality Assurance and Accreditation, Engineering Skills

Keywords: Engineering education, Framework regulations, Evaluation of implementation, Engineering skills

INTRODUCTION

The Norwegian Ministry of Education and Research adopted on 3rd of February 2011 new framework regulations for engineering education, composed of mandatory regulations and supporting guidelines. A national strategic academic body for the STEM-field within the Norwegian Association of Higher Educational Institutions, UHR-MNT, is mandated with an active role in relation to the guidelines and will propose

revisions when needed. Based on the framework, the engineering education has been approved by FEANI (Fédération Européenne d'Associations Nationales d'Ingénieurs).

After the regulations were implemented, there have been major structural changes in the Norwegian higher educational sector. Several mergers were implemented in 2016, and as the merged institutions are working to operationalize their new structures, the aligning of study programs is crucial. The merger processes are now completed, and engineering education is offered at fewer and somewhat larger institutions. A national evaluation of these study programs has been initiated; the main goals are quality development and experience exchange.

This paper will present the background for the evaluation of the implementation of the framework regulations for engineering education in Norway, the process for the evaluation, formal and societal changes crucial to engineering education, successes and failures of implementation of the framework as well as other national tools developed to support the on-going quality development process. In the conclusion, a way forward is described.

1 BACKGROUND

1.1 A competence based framework for engineering education

Norwegian engineering education is controlled by a mandatory framework – including guidelines anchored in the regulations. The guidelines are expected to be in a process of continuous improvement. The regulations were adopted by the Norwegian Ministry of Education and Research in February 2011, based on a national development process involving different stakeholders. The description of the learning outcomes for all engineering candidates is the central and most important part of the regulations. It was implemented by universities and university colleges in 2011 and 2012. The vision of the work was “The Engineer – community committed, creative and empowered, with the ability to actively contribute to the challenges of the future”! The following topics were chosen as focus areas to improve within the education programs: ICT proficiency, corporate social responsibility, ethics and the engineer's role in society, systems thinking, integration of theory and practice, co-operation and student mobility, interdisciplinarity, innovation and entrepreneurship, research based education, environmental concern as well as transition between bachelors and masters level, which is strongly dependent on the STEM-base within the programs.

The regulations and the development of this competence based framework for engineering education is further presented in [1].

1.2 Implementation

Based on a national survey of stakeholders within universities and university colleges, theory and the objectives of the new curriculum, attributes that may be associated with quality education were suggested as part of the national guidelines. Successful implementation of the new engineering education was expected to provide an engineering education with the following characteristics:

- Integrated and holistic
- ‘Cutting edge’ by means of professional updating
- Updated and including varied learning and evaluation methods
- Research and development orientation
- Professional competence and practical skills
- International competence

- Interdisciplinarity, innovation and entrepreneurship
- Study effort and coping
- Engineering enculturation

Against this background, an evaluation process of the results from implementing the competence based framework for engineering education was initiated in 2016, by UHR-MNT.

2 PROCESS

The evaluation process is the product of a national working group, local self-evaluation groups, an on-line survey of staff and students in universities and university colleges and national workshops with institutional representatives. The local self-evaluation was carried out by a broad-based group at each institution. Both faculty management, management at the department and study program level, as well as academic staff, administrative staff and students were represented. Eight institutions have been part of the self-evaluation, most of them with several campuses – which at the time of implementation were independent institutions. 980 respondents answered a questionnaire comprising 37 questions, with partly selected questions to different respondents. Respondents were management, staff and students. The main body of questions were based on indicators of the characteristics listed in section 1. The answers from the survey were made available to the self-evaluation groups. The self-evaluation groups also answered a questionnaire with three groups of questions: overall, related to the main themes and detailed questions on selected areas. Two national meetings with 50 and 55 participants each have discussed the results from the survey and the self-evaluations carried out by the institutions, with focus on experiences and challenges identified by the national working group. The process itself has identified several good examples and experiences from which everyone will benefit. Shared experiences that can contribute to continuous improvement of the programs are part of the results from the evaluation. These will be further presented and discussed in section 5.

3 FORMAL CHANGES AND SOCIETAL CHANGES

3.1 Structural changes in the Norwegian higher education sector

During the implementation period, there have been major structural changes in the Norwegian higher educational sector. Norway must adapt to meet social changes and to ensure jobs and welfare in the future. An important goal is increased quality in higher education and research. Therefore, a report to Norway's National Parliament No. 18 (2014-2015) "Concentration for Quality – Structural Reform in the University and University College Sector", has resulted in a fundamental reorganization of the Norwegian university and university college sector. The higher educational resources are now concentrated at fewer but stronger institutions. The goal has been to establish a structure for tomorrow's knowledge society. This change has significantly affected engineering education. The evaluation results, supporting processes and the way forward that are presented in the next sections should be seen in this context.

3.2 Quality culture in higher education

Over recent years, there has been considerable attention to quality in education on both a national, political level and the institutional level. The Government has the last years been paving the way for increased quality at universities and university colleges by various means. The report to Norway's National Parliament No. 7 (2014-2015)

“Long-term plan for research and higher education”, the structural change described in section 3.1, adjustments in financial systems for universities and university colleges, simplified goal-oriented management and revised regulations for academic quality, are all examples of this.

Some important goals for the extensive work on developing a culture for quality in higher education is given in another Government white paper, the report to Norway’s National Parliament No. 16 (2016-2017) Quality Culture in Higher Education [2]:

- Demanding and engaging studies
- Students integrated in the academic community
- Clear learning goals and holistic programs
- Varied learning and assessment methods
- Collaboration with working life
- Teachers with good educational skills
- Teaching should be valued higher

NOKUT, the Norwegian Agency for Quality Assurance in Education, has in 2017 established a new regulation on supervising the education quality of higher education (the study supervisory regulation) [3]. The goal is to ensure high quality in Norwegian higher education. NOKUT’s Director explains: “With the new study supervisory regulation, we are turning our quality work even more clearly towards what happens at the level of study offerings. This is where the students meet the subject and the academic community, and the institution must facilitate the students’ learning and ensure that they achieve the planned learning outcome”.

3.3 Thematic changes

In the current framework regulations there are high-level learning outcomes specified for five selected fields of engineering – civil engineering, computer engineering, electrical engineering, chemical engineering and mechanical engineering, as these had been dominant for a long time; this is no longer the case. Educational provision now combines some of these five fields, i.e. as Mechatronics or Fire Safety Engineering, and includes sub-fields, or programs not at all related to these long established fields. Hence, this has to be taken into account when the current framework is to be updated.

Since the current framework was designed, safety and security have become only increasingly important for an engineer to be aware of and able to handle. Hence, this has to be explicitly built into the framework for the future.

Further, the importance of knowledge and skills of chemistry have likewise increased alongside the environmental focus over the last years. The knowledge and skills of chemistry needed for this focus are not the same as those that were in focus just a decade ago. Once more, the framework for the future has to reflect this.

Finally, ICT knowledge and skills were of course included in the current framework. However, the corresponding learning outcomes were not sufficiently well specified – perhaps nearly taken for granted, and they have to be updated and upgraded – including an explicit coupling to safety and security.

4 SUCCESSES AND FAILURES

The self-evaluation in broad working groups has aimed to map the positive effects that can be experienced from implementing the regulations and supporting guidelines, as

well as unintended effects that should be followed up with adjustments and revision of national regulations.

4.1 Sharing of good examples

The self-evaluation groups are satisfied with the high-level learning outcomes for the engineering studies. Some described the learning outcomes as somewhat over-ambitious, but after discussions in the national meetings, it was decided to retain these learning outcomes unchanged.

The framework regulations focus on an integrated and holistic education. The institutions describe it as an advantage that the guidelines also cover a description of the different paths to enter engineering education, including a vocational path via apprenticeship, and common requirements for transition from bachelor in engineering to master in technology.

To meet the society's need for higher education, several institutions emphasize how programs are developed in close interaction with local industry. Some institutions also offer work place experience that awards academic credits.

Professional knowledge is emphasized in the new framework regulations. In the first year all programs include an introduction to professional engineering practice and working methods. For most institutions part of this is common for all engineering students (e.g. history of technology, project management, environment and society, introduction to laboratory and research methods), with another part directed towards each program or branch of study. Project based learning is common and the students are also introduced to general competences such as group dynamics and how to handle conflict.

To get a closer connection between professions and academia some of the institutions describe how the students at an early stage are introduced to academic learning activities. Analysis, critical thinking and scientific methods start being connected in the course "introduction to professional engineering practice and working methods" in one of the first semesters and ends with the bachelor thesis in the last semester.

In the 5th semester the students may choose between optional specialization, student exchange or work place experience.

4.2 Improvement areas

The current framework regulations had to include a lot of new learning outcomes compared to earlier versions – due to the extended knowledge and skills needed in general by an engineer. This may have been perceived as leaving too little room for making different study programs unique within an institution and across institutions. This should be alleviated by introducing some additional flexibility in the framework regulations.

The teaching and assessment methods used in the Norwegian engineering education have been fairly 'traditional'. More varied teaching methods – like flipped classroom approaches, and more modern assessment methods – including digital exams, are gradually being introduced to secure the achievement of the learning outcomes on different levels. However, there is still considerable room for development.

Establishing the current framework introduced several meeting arenas for national benchmarking of the different educational provision. However, there has not been much focus on international benchmarking – like peer-to-peer evaluation of study

programs between institutions in different countries. Hence, there is also a potential for improvement here.

The current framework is also structured so that it enables students to spend one out of six semesters at another institution outside Norway. To date, too few students have taken advantage of this possibility, so other measures have to be applied to increase the rate of student exchanges.

5 OTHER TOOLS

The work has resulted in concrete actions and cooperation between the institutions. Especially, there has been increased variation in learning and assessment methods. The MNT-conference was established in 2015. The conference is aimed at teachers in STEM-subjects at university-level that are close to the students, knowing what is difficult within these subjects, having experience with different teaching methods and knowing what the students struggle to master [4,5]. The conference is a meeting place where teachers within STEM-subjects can document and share experiences with each other and others active within STEM-education, including institutional managers and students. The second conference was held in 2017, and the evaluation showed it was a success.

The Nordic Journal of STEM Education has also been established. This is a peer-reviewed, open-access journal publishing in the broad field of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Education. Contributions that address pedagogical, educational, and academic developments or studies are invited. The journal is planning for two main sections: one for contributions based in the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning (SoTL) and in empirical observation and theoretical frameworks, and one that reports and reflects on the use of “good practice”. Experience, reflection and scholarly studies can be shared in support of the development of higher education. After the MNT-conference the authors are invited to further develop their contributions into full papers for peer-review and publication in the Nordic Journal of STEM Education. The journal will be classified on level 1 in the Norwegian two-tier scientific classification system.

6 THE WAY FORWARD

In the last few years the framework for education in Norway has changed a lot. There has been an increased focus on educational competence. For example, all universities and university colleges shall by 2019 have a pedagogical merit system. It is also expected that peer-review and peer monitoring of teaching will be implemented. The Government has also built a competence-based arena for quality in education, i.e. the Centres for Excellence in Education Initiative. The framework for Engineering Education aims to follow up and strengthen these changes.

In the future, a web site for engineering education will be established with the current framework and the corresponding regulatory descriptions. This should open up for a more continuous development of different study programs and other related educational provision. This change will also be accompanied by an extended use of professional forums where teachers and researchers meet to discuss, propose and facilitate enhancement of programs and provision.

Already now, there is a need to change the framework regulations’ minimum subject size, some exemption provisions and the scope of the bachelor thesis. There are also

challenges with the division into subject groups, topics, subjects, specialization topics and electives, in terms of size, content and naming.

As already indicated in section 4.1, some institutions have reported that the learning outcome descriptions may be too ambitious. Compared with overall expectations of the higher educational sector, the level and extent should still be appropriate. However, concepts such as 'insight into' versus 'knowledge' and 'skills' are important in this context, and clarifications are needed here.

After implementing the current framework regulations, it has not been possible to see any clear effect in some designated areas – e.g. drop out or gender distribution. Further, it has been difficult to decide whether other perceived effects – like more research based focus, are the outcome of the current framework or other changes – like the ones discussed in section 3. Both these aspects need to be further checked with the proposed changes of the framework.

7 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Some findings are:

- The common engineering base that is fundamental in the curriculum has been difficult to implement, but there are also many examples of good solutions. These will be used by the different institutions to improve their own programs and provision.
- Appropriate digital and environmental skills along with different aspects of engineering enculturation have not been integrated as well as they should. This has to get a clear focus in the future.
- A minimum course size of 10 ECTS is found to be too rigid. This should be changed to a smaller minimum amount, but at the same time limiting the maximum number of course exams to be taken each semester.

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